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FEATURES OF PSYCHOEMOTIONAL DISORDERS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH COVID-19 PNEUMONIA

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ABSTRACT

This article studies to conduct a structural analysis of disorders of the psycho-emotional status of perinatal women with pneumonia COVID-19. The prospective study included 3080 pregnant women infected with SARS-CoV-2, of which 889 were in the 1st trimester, 1056 in the 2nd and 1135 in the 3rd trimester of pregnancy. The vast majority (64.3%; 1980 out of 3080) of cases were diagnosed with a moderate course of COVID-19 pneumonia. Identification and assessment of the severity of psycho-emotional disorders were carried out according to the General Anxiety Disorder-7 scale (GAD-7), Impact of Event Scale-6 (IES-6) and Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). A high incidence of mixed psycho-emotional disorders was typical for pregnant women with severe and highly severe COVID-19 pneumonia - 46.7% and 52.7%, respectively, which indicates an aggravation of the clinical picture of psycho-emotional disorders against the background of the progression of COVID-19 pneumonia. Psycho-emotional disorders associated with COVID-19 infection are characteristic of a significant proportion of pregnant women. At the same time, their early detection using specialized questionnaire scales (GAD-7, IES-6 and PHQ-9) can contribute to the timely involvement of the psychological component of therapeutic tactics and prevent adverse perinatal and social consequences.

Keywords: pregnancy, COVID-19 pneumonia, anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ НАРУШЕНИЙ У ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНЫХ ЖЕНЩИН С ПНЕВМОНИЕЙ COVID-19

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье исследуется проведение структурного анализа нарушений психоэмоционального статуса перинатальных женщин с пневмонией COVID-19. Проспективное исследование включало 3080 беременных женщин, инфицированных SARS-CoV-2, из них 889 находились на 1-м триместре, 1056 – на 2-м и 1135 – на 3-м триместре беременности. В подавляющем большинстве (64,3%; 1980 из 3080) случаев диагностировано среднетяжелое течение пневмонии COVID-19. Выявление и оценка степени тяжести психоэмоциональных нарушений проводились по шкалам оценки тревожных расстройств ГТР-7, посттравматических стрессовых расстройств (ПТСР) IES-6, и депрессивного синдрома PHQ-9. Высокая частота встречаемости смешанных психоэмоциональных расстройств была характерна для беременных женщин с пневмонией COVID-19 тяжелой и крайне тяжелой степени – 46,7% и 52,7% соответственно, что свидетельствует об усугублении клинической картины психоэмоциональных нарушений на фоне прогрессирования пневмонии COVID-19. Психоэмоциональные нарушения на фоне инфицирования COVID-19 характерны для значительной части беременных женщин. При этом их раннее выявление с использованием специализированных шкал-опросников может способствовать своевременному подключению психологической составляющей терапевтической тактики и предупредить неблагоприятные перинатальные и социальные последствия.

Ключевые слова: беременность, пневмония COVID-19, тревога, депрессия, посттравматическое стрессовое расстройство.

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КЎП АЪЗОЛАР ЕТИШМОВЧИЛИГИ ВА ИНТЕНСИВ ТЕРАПИЯ СИНДРОМИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ БИЛАН АСОРАТЛАНГАН COVID-19 БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН ҲОМИЛАДОР АЁЛЛАРНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола кўп аъзолар етишмовчилиги ва интенсив терапия синдроми ривожланиши билан асоратланган COVID-19 билан касалланган ҳомиладор аёлларнинг психологик ҳолатини ўрганишга бағишланган. 2020-йилнинг декабридан 2022-йил 01-январига қадар COVID-19 пандемияси даврида SARS-CoV-2 инфекциясини юктирган ва "Зангиота-1

Республика ихтисослаштирилган юкумли касалликлар шифохонаси" туғруқ бўлимида давлоланган 3080 нафар ҳомиладор аёл. Тадқиқот даврида COVID-19 пневмонияси билан касалланган ҳомиладор аёлларнинг 22,0% реанимация бўлимларида интенсив терапияга муҳтож эди. Кўп аъзолар етишмовчилиги ривожланиши билан ҳолатларнинг умумий тахлилий намунада 9,0%-ни ташкил этди. Ўлим ҳолатларининг аксарияти ўта оғир кечадиган ва психо-эмоционал ҳолатнинг аралаш патологияси бўлган аёллар орасида қайд этилган – 44-та ҳолат. Дастлабки ҳолатга кўра, аёлларнинг 56,6% эмоционал стрессни бошдан кечирган, 26,7% ташвишли касалликларга дуч келган ва 16,7% депрессияга учраган. Туғруқдан кейинги даврда стресс ҳолат, ташвиш ва депрессиянинг комбинацияси 46,1% ҳолларда (677 тадан 312 тасида) аниқланган, бу эрта туғилиш ва абортлар билан аёллар учун хосдир. COVID-19 билан учинчи триместрдаги ҳомиладор аёллар кўп аъзолар етишмовчилигига кўпроқ мойил бўлган.

Калит сўзлар: COVID-19, пневмония, ҳомиладорлик, психоэмоционал касалликлар, ташвиш, депрессия, стресс, реанимация ва интенсив терапия, кўп аъзолар етишмовчилиги.

Introduction

According to WHO COVID-19 pandemic has become a global problem of the world health care most acutely affects women at different stages of the perinatal period, from conception to delivery, as well as in the postpartum period [1, 2]. It is known that during pregnancy, against changes in the immune and cardiopulmonary system, favorable conditions are created for developing respiratory viral infections [3]. Currently, there is conflicting evidence regarding the greater susceptibility of pregnant women to COVID-19 infection and there are no specific recommendations regarding diagnosis, treatment, and psychosocial support in pregnancy with COVID-19 [4]. It has been noted that the clinical presentation of pregnant women with COVID-19 infection is comparable to that of infected non-pregnant women, and frequent symptoms include fever, cough, myalgia, sore throat, and [5].

Studies have shown that mortality in COVID-19 among pregnant women reaches 25%, the rate of preterm delivery is 4.3% to 25.0%, pre-eclampsia 5.9%, miscarriage 14.5%, premature rupture of membranes 9.2% and fetal growth retardation 2.8-25.0% [6].

The impact of the pandemic on the psychological and emotional state of pregnant women and women in the immediate postpartum period remains the most acute and understudied problem. For example, a number of studies have shown that pregnant women have the highest rates of depression, anxiety and stress, which may be exacerbated by the pandemic context of COVID-19 [7, 8, 9].

Also, it has been noted that pregnant women who have experienced severe stress associated with COVID-19 infection have the highest risk of adverse perinatal outcomes [10]. Most clinicians seek to better understand its phenomenology by emphasizing the content of collective anxiety through various content analyses and developing systemic approaches to psycho correction of the resulting conditions, which will significantly mitigate obstetric and somatic complications that occur during pregnancy as a consequence of stress [11, 12, 13].

Based on the above, the study aimed to conduct a structural analysis of disorders of the psychoemotional status of perinatal women with COVID-19 pneumonia.

Research material and methods. The basis of the study was the results of the examination and treatment of 3080 pregnant women and young mothers infected with SARS-CoV-2 during the COVID-19 pandemic in the maternity ward of the "Zangiota-1 Republican Specialized Infectious Hospital" from December 2020 to January 01, 2022.

Most women (48.0%; 1478 of 3080) were in the age range of 26-30 years, and most women (84.0%; 2586 of 3080) had no history of miscarriage. In terms of the number of pregnancies in the history of miscarriage, cases with two (31.0%; 956 of 3080) and one pregnancy (27.5%; 847 of 3080) in the history of miscarriage were the most common. Only 5.9% (183 of 3080) of pregnant women were primiparous (Table 1). At the time of admission, 889 of 3080 women (28.9%) were in their first trimester of pregnancy (<13 weeks gestation), 1056 women (34.3%) in their second

trimester (13-27 weeks gestation), and 1,135 women (36.8%) were in their third trimester (≥ 28 weeks gestation) the most. According to the international criteria for evaluating the severity of infection, COVID-19, an intermediate course of pneumonia, was diagnosed in most pregnant women (64.3%; 1980 out of 3080). The clinical presentation of pregnant women with COVID-19 infection was bilateral pneumonia in 48.0% (1478 of 3080). According to MSCT, the majority (60.0%; 1848 of 3080) of patients had up to 50% lung lesions.

The extragenital diseases were diagnosed in 1232 of 3080 (40.0%) patients. They were represented by: vegetovascular dystonia, various degrees of hypertension, chronic bronchitis, tonsillitis, chronic pyelonephritis, chronic gastritis, colitis, pancreatitis, autoimmune thyroiditis, metabolic syndrome, obesity, and myopia. There was a combination of different diseases in 943 patients. History of gynecological diseases: cervical ectopy, inflammatory diseases of the uterus and its appendages, ovarian tumors and tumor-like masses, uterine myoma, ectopic pregnancy, and infertility of different genesis were in 914 patients.

Table 1.

General characteristics of pregnant women with COVID-19 (n=3080)

Indicator	n	%
Age		
18-25 y.o.	998	32,4%
26-30 y.o.	1478	48,0%
31-40 y.o.	604	19,6%
A history of pregnancy		
0	183	5,9%
1	847	27,5%
2	956	31,0%
3	522	16,9%
4	572	18,6%
A history of miscarriages		
0	2586	84,0%
1	432	14,0%
2	44	1,4%
3	16	0,6%
Pregnancy status		
1 trimester	889	28,9%
2 trimester	1056	34,3%
3 trimester	1135	36,8%
The severity of COVID-19 pneumonia		
Mild degree	536	17,4%
Mild severity	1980	64,3%;
Severe course	490	15,9%
Extremely severe course	74	2,4%
The volume of lung tissue damage		
CT-1, less than 25% of the lungs are affected	524	17,0%
CT-2, 25-50% of lungs are affected	1324	43,0%
CT-3, 50-75% of lungs are affected	1106	35,9%
CT-4, more than 75% of lungs are affected	126	4,1%

Detecting and assessing the severity of psycho-emotional disorders were performed using the GTR-7 anxiety assessment scale, the IES-6 posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) assessment scale, and the PHQ-9 depressive syndrome assessment scale. Conjoint psychoemotional pathology was diagnosed by the particular combined PHQ-ADS scale, which was a sum of the scores of the

PHQ-9 and GTR-7 questionnaires (maximum score was 48, and a combination of PTSD, anxiety and depression was revealed at 20 points or more).

Results. According to the results of completion of specialized scales and questionnaires for the entire period of study, a significant part (80,1%; 2467 out of 3080 women) scored at or above threshold values, which was characteristic for moderate and severe posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), moderate and severe anxiety, and clinically significant depression. Of the psychoemotional disturbances, 54.3% (1671 of 3080) were PTSD (≥ 2.0 on the IES-6 scale), 13.4% (413 of 3080) had moderate to severe anxiety (≥ 5 on the GTR-7 scale), and 12.4% (383 of 3080) women (≥ 10 on the PHQ-9 scale) were depressed in varying degrees.

Figure 1. Results of psychoemotional disturbances assessment in pregnant women with COVID-19 using specialized scales

Thus, in more than half of the cases, we encountered PTSD, of which 712 cases (23.0% of 3080) were diagnosed as comorbid psycho-emotional disorders, i.e. clinical manifestations of anxiety and/or depression joined the existing disorders (Fig. 1, Table 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of women with COVID-19 pneumonia by gestational status

Based on gestational age at the time of admission of women with COVID-19 pneumonia, gestational age up to 13 weeks (first trimester) was dominated by PTSD, which was detected in 42.0% (374 of 889) cases. Also, in the first trimester, depressive states were observed in 19.8% (176 of 889) cases and anxiety disorders in 9.2% (82 of 889) (Table 2). Thus, the incidence of various psychoemotional disorders in pregnant women with COVID-19 infection in the first trimester of pregnancy was 71.1% (632 of 889).

In the second trimester of pregnancy (13-27 weeks of gestation), PTSD, anxiety, or depression of moderate to severe severity, as assessed by the IES-6, GTR-7, and PHQ-9 scales, were observed in 100% (1056 of 1056 cases). PTSD had the highest frequency (68.0%, 718 of 1,056) (Table 2). In terms of the incidence of comorbid psychoemotional pathology in COVID-19 pregnancies, this gestational period also had statistically significant high numbers relative to other

trimesters, 50.6% (534 of 1056) versus 2.7% (24 of 889) in the first trimester and 13.6% (154 of 1135) in the third trimester (Table 2). Women in the third trimester of pregnancy (≥ 28 weeks' gestation) also had the highest incidence of PTSD, at 51.0% (579 of 1135). Anxiety disorders were diagnosed in 11.1% (126 of 1135) cases, and depressive states were the lowest, accounting for 6.5% (74 of 1135).

Table 2.

Distribution of patients by survey results in the analytic sample as a whole and by pregnancy status

	1 trimester, <13 weeks (n=889)	2 trimester, 13-27 weeks (n=1056)	3 trimester, ≥ 28 weeks (n=1135)	Total (n=3080)
IES-6				
≥ 2	374 (42,0%)	718 (68,0%)	579 (51,0%)	1671 (54,3%)
< 2	515 (58,0%)	338 (32,0%)	556 (49,0%)	1409 (45,7%)
GAD-7				
≥ 5	82 (9,2%)	205 (19,4%)	126 (11,1%)	413 (13,4%)
≤ 4	807 (90,8%)	851 (80,6%)	1009 (88,9%)	2667 (86,6%)
PHQ-9				
≥ 10	176 (19,8%)	133 (12,6%)	74 (6,5%)	383 (12,4%)
≤ 9	713 (80,2%)	923 (87,4%)	1061 (93,5%)	2697 (87,6%)
PHQ-ADS				
≥ 19	24 (2,7%)	534 (50,6%)	154 (13,6%)	712 (23,0%)
≤ 18	865 (97,3%)	522 (49,4%)	981 (86,4%)	2368 (77,0%)
Total				
+	632 (71,1%)	1056 (100%)	779 (68,6%)	2467 (80,1%)
-	257 (28,9%)	0 (0,0%)	356 (31,4%)	613 (19,9%)

Figure 3. Distribution of pregnant women by clinical severity of COVID-19 pneumonia with the frequency of psycho-emotional disturbances

Table 3:

Distribution of patients in the analytic sample by the severity of COVID-19 pneumonia.

	Light degree COVID-19 (n=536)	Medium-severe COVID-19 (n=1980)	Severe COVID-19 (n=490)	Extremely severe (n=74)	Total (n=3080)
IES-6					
≥ 2	188 (35,1%)	1178 (59,5%)	266 (54,3%)	39 (52,7%)	1671 (54,3%)
< 2	348 (64,9%)	802 (40,5%)	224 (45,7%)	35 (47,3%)	1409 (45,7%)
GAD-7					

≥ 5	52 (9,7%)	200 (10,1%)	140 (28,6%)	21 (28,4%)	413 (13,4%)
≤ 4	484 (90,3%)	1780 (89,9%)	350 (71,4%)	53 (71,6%)	2667 (86,6%)
PHQ-9					
≥ 10	78 (14,6%)	207 (10,5%)	84 (17,1%)	14 (18,9%)	383 (12,4%)
≤ 9	458 (85,4%)	1773 (89,5%)	406 (82,9%)	60 (81,1%)	2697 (87,6%)
PHQ-ADS					
≥ 19	0 (0,0%)	444 (22,4%)	229 (46,7%)	39 (52,7%)	712 (23,0%)
≤ 18	536 (100%)	1536 (77,6%)	261 (53,3%)	35 (47,3%)	2368 (77,0%)
Total					
+	318 (59,3%)	1585 (80%)	490 (100%)	74 (100%)	2467 (80,1%)
-	218 (40,7%)	395 (20%)	0 (0,0%)	0 (0,0%)	613 (19,9%)

A relatively high incidence of psycho-emotional disorders (51.5%; 1585 out of 3080) was detected in the COVID-19 moderate course cohort (n=1980) (Figure 3). In the COVID-19 moderate course pneumonia cohort itself, most of the women (59.5%; 1178 of 1980) had a PTSD clinic (more than 2 points on the IES-6 scale), and the rest had pure anxiety (10.1%; 200 of 1980; more than 5 points on GTR-7) and depression (10.5%; 207 of 1980; more than 10 points on the PHQ-9 scale) conditions (Table 3, Figure 4). PTSD had almost equal frequency among pregnant women with COVID-19 severe and extremely severe (54.3% and 52.7%, respectively), as did anxiety (28.6% and 28.4%, respectively) and depressive (17.1% and 18.9%, respectively) conditions.

Figure 4. Frequency of psycho-emotional disturbances at different degrees of COVID-19 pneumonia severity

The high frequency of mixed psycho-emotional disorders assessed by the PHQ-ADS scale above 19 points was typical for pregnant women with severe and extremely severe COVID-19

pneumonia - 46.7% and 52.7%, respectively (Figure 4, Table 3). Thus, with a worsening clinical picture of COVID-19 pneumonia, there was a 100% prevalence of psycho-emotional disorders.

Purely depressive syndrome had high frequency in the first trimester, manifested in the second trimester with significantly low frequency, and had the lowest frequency in the third trimester. This was associated with increased numbers of women with PTSD and combinations of depression and anxiety as pregnancy status increased.

Discussion. With the COVID-19 pandemic, virtually all clinicians note a significant increase in psychoemotional disorders. For example, S.M. Green et al. (2021) conducted a study involving 84 pregnant women, of whom one-third of participants had major concerns related to the impact of COVID-19 on the course of pregnancy, and 40% of concerns were related to the perinatal context [14].

An anonymous online cross-sectional survey of pregnant and parenting women was conducted in 64 countries between May and June 2020. Data from these surveys were posted on the Pregistry platform for COVID-19 research (<https://corona.pregistry.com>) in 12 languages. Participants completed measures of demographics, COVID-19 exposure and anxiety, and mental health symptoms, including posttraumatic stress on the IES-6 scale, anxiety/depression on the PHQ-4 scale, and loneliness on the UCLA scale. 3 [15, 16]. Of the 6894 participants, a significant proportion of women scored at or above the thresholds for elevated PTSD (2979 [43%]), anxiety/depression (2138 [31%]), and loneliness (3691 [53%]). The most frequently reported concerns were pregnancy and childbirth, including the inability to visit relatives after delivery (59%), COVID-19 infection of the baby (59%), and lack of support during childbirth (55%). COVID-19 is causing changes in birth plans (41%). Greater anxiety related to children (i.e., inadequate child care, risk of infection) and missing doctor visits were associated with significantly higher odds of posttraumatic stress disorder, anxiety/depression, and loneliness [15, 16].

T. Farrell et al. (2020) also found a high prevalence of anxiety and depressive symptoms (34.4% and 39.2%, respectively) on the PHQ-ADS scale in Qatar, one of the most economically developed countries in the world [17].

S. Alfayumi-Zeadna et al (2020) assessed the prevalence of perinatal depression symptoms during the COVID-19 pandemic among Arab and Jewish women in Israel. The sample included 730 perinatal women (604 Jewish and 126 Arab women). The prevalence of perinatal depression in the entire study population was 40%, significantly higher among Arab women than among Jewish women (58% vs. 36%, $p < 0.001$). Higher values of perinatal depression were significantly associated with symptoms of anxiety ($p < 0.001$) and COVID-19 stress ($p < 0.001$) [18].

M. Ceulemans et al (2021) conducted a study on 9041 women with COVID-19 (including 3907 pregnant and 5134 lactating women). The prevalence of major depressive symptoms was 15% in the pregnant cohort and 13% in the breastfeeding cohort. Moderate to severe symptoms of generalized anxiety were found in 11% and 10% of pregnant and breastfeeding women. Risk factors associated with poor mental health were: the presence of chronic mental illness, chronic somatic diseases in the postpartum period, smoking, unplanned pregnancy, and occupational status [19].

Our study involving 3080 pregnant women showed the effect of pregnancy status on the prevalence of psychoemotional status disorders in each gestational period. Thus, women with PTSD and combinations of depression and anxiety were significantly more in the second trimester of pregnancy and had a lower frequency among women in the first trimester, as was shown by partial and overall structural analysis. The effect of COVID-19 pneumonia severity on the incidence of anxiety disorders and co-occurring psycho-emotional status disorders in pregnancy. Many pregnant women with psychoemotional disorders (51.5%; 1,585 of 3,080) were assigned to the COVID-19 moderate severity cohort.

The discussion can be summarized by the results of a study obtained by Q. Chen et al (2022) showed that the COVID-19 pandemic can deleteriously affect women's mental health after childbirth. A study of the prevalence and risk factors for depression among postpartum women could shed some light on their psycho-emotional state. This would suggest various support measures and specialized interventions during the COVID-19 pandemic to improve maternal and

infant outcomes. Much more research on the psychological well-being of mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic in middle- and low-income countries was strongly recommended by the authors [20].

Conclusion. Psycho-emotional disturbances during COVID-19 infection characterized a significant proportion (80.1%; 2467 of 3080) of pregnant women, with a 100% (n=1056) rate in the second trimester of pregnancy. Depressive syndrome was most frequently detected in the first trimester, and anxiety states and PTSD were more common in women in the second trimester of pregnancy. The number of women with PTSD and combinations of depression and anxiety also increased as the pregnancy status increased. A high incidence of mixed psycho-emotional disorders was found among pregnant women with severe and extremely severe COVID-19 pneumonia, 46.7% and 52.7%, respectively, indicating that the clinical picture of psycho-emotional disorders worsened with COVID-19 pneumonia progression.

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